

MODERN FOUNDATIONS OF TEACHING ECONOMICS IN UNIVERSITY

¹Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadkulovna

teacher, Samarkand State University veterinary medicine of livestock and biotechnologies, Samarkand,

²Raximova Umida Rabbimovna

teacher, Samarkand State University veterinary medicine of livestock and biotechnologies, Samarkand.

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i02-p4-154>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17th February 2023

Accepted: 26th February 2023

Online: 27th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Fundamental training, master's program, target specialization, basic discipline, opportunity, masters-economists-analysts, development, globalization, economic science, economic policy.

ABSTRACT

At present, the problem of methods of teaching economics is becoming more and more urgent in our country. We are witnessing a reform of the higher education system. Increasing attention is paid to independent work. Other trends are also noticeable. The purpose of this article is to study the basics of teaching methods in general and economic disciplines in particular, as well as to analyze the main trends in the development of higher economic education in Uzbekistan.

The events of recent years in Uzbekistan have led, firstly, to the organizational transformation of the higher education system into a university system and, secondly, to the widespread training of economists in educational institutions of various profiles. For the country, this gave rise to more than one problem.

Based on the established content of university education, how to ensure the university level of economic training in all the universities that have appeared, where there are or have opened economic faculties?

Since university training presupposes an appropriate personnel potential of teaching and research personnel, it is important to find out how and in what timeframe it is possible to form such a potential in new universities.

The fundamental nature of economic education at universities is ensured, as a rule, by the thoroughness of the study of economic theory. In this regard, should we consider the university training of economists in "applied" universities, where the emphasis is on branch economic disciplines and, in essence, specialists with a narrow profile are graduating [1].

The international community has developed a number of criteria for university education, including economics. Given these criteria, how to develop international cooperation in the field of economic education; how much should be taken into account along with the American and European Asian experience in this area.

National regulation of university economic education in modern conditions does not exclude the use of market indicators to determine the ranking of universities. However, such procedures should not be opportunistic or promotional in nature.

At all times there has been a problem of the relationship between economic education and economic practice. This problem has become especially acute in Uzbekistan in recent years.

What should be the basis of training - an ideal model of a market economy or the solution of real economic issues? Is it possible to combine both in the educational process and what should be their optimal ratio?

The systemic nature of economic education helps to comprehensively perceive reality and the prospects for its change. The interdependence of economic processes, their conditionality, on the one hand, by established patterns, and, on the other hand, by the subjective actions of real people, objectively increases the role of fundamental training of managers and professionals of various levels in the management hierarchy of state and non-state structures.

The universality of market principles presupposes an economic evaluation or justification for any action in society. This means that there is a kind of market atmosphere for the formation of a person along the entire educational path: family - school - university - work. It is important that the deformation of market reforms in Uzbekistan does not lead to the deformation of economic education[2].

A key link in economic education is the development of economic theory. In turn, the most important lever of influence on economic practice is economic policy. The effectiveness of economic policy depends not only on the degree of implementation of the conclusions and recommendations of economic theory.

Modern economic theory is not a monolith, it is a combination of various schools and directions. However, the teaching of economic theory should be systematic and integral. It is this approach to teaching that makes it possible to count on the most effective impact of economic education on real economic policy.

The experience of real economic policy in foreign countries and in Uzbekistan over a long historical period indicates that the greatest effectiveness is achieved when policy is based not on one scientific school or direction, but on a combination of them. This combination is different and depends on the specific country and the political orientation of the government. One of the explanations for this situation is the fact of the development of a mixed economy in all developed countries.

Crisis phenomena in the world economy in 2007-2009 are forcing international economic organizations to seek solutions to numerous problems also in a combination of various theoretical approaches and views. The universality of market relations in the world and the growing development of globalization objectively increase the role of economic science in shaping national and international economic policy at the turn of the third millennium [3].

University economic education in its content and form allows you to be prepared to the greatest extent for modern challenges at various levels of management - corporate, national, international.

The fundamental nature of university economic education does not exclude, but, on the contrary, presupposes a certain specialization of students. Just as new branches continue to form in the economy, new branches of science are emerging in the system of economic

sciences. This process has especially intensified in Uzbekistan during the transition to a market economy. There is also specialization according to country features and functions of certain segments of the market mechanism.

The fundamental nature of training is provided throughout the vertical of education, and does not mean the study of basic disciplines only in the initial courses. In a certain sense, the three-level system contributes to the optimal ratio of fundamental and special training: bachelor's degree - master's degree - postgraduate study. Three levels of training in economic education meet the most diverse requirements of a market economy [4].

Bachelor's degree provides basic training for the most massive circle of economists. At this level of training, specialization can occur both according to the sectoral principle, and according to the degree of development and use of mathematical methods for analyzing the economy. At the same time, it is important that the optimal ratio of compulsory courses and elective courses be found. Not always the abundance of elective courses gives the best result. In turn, the "averaging" of mathematics for all undergraduate students does not allow for graduates with in-depth mathematical training.

Continuing fundamental training in the master's program is already directly associated with the target specialization, enshrined in the master's program. At this level, specialization is also provided in the basic disciplines. This creates the opportunity to prepare masters-economists-analysts not for the country or the economy as a whole, but for individual areas of activity in accordance with the predicted market demand for professionals of this level.

A graduate of a master's program, when entering a graduate school, deepens his specialization already in the field of scientific research. The demand for professionals of this kind is piecemeal in a market economy. Only a solid and comprehensive fundamental training allows graduate students to do a truly relevant and in-depth PhD research. This is ensured by a special program of work with graduate students at the faculty and departments [5].

The preparation of bachelors and masters also has an international aspect. If we proceed from the worldwide spread of market principles, as well as from the target task of training personnel for a market economy, then the general system of such education is precisely two-tier training: bachelor-master.

Summing up the work done, we can draw the following main conclusions about the system of higher economic education in Uzbekistan and the methodology of teaching economic disciplines.

The events of recent years in Uzbekistan have led, firstly, to the organizational transformation of the higher education system into a university system and, secondly, to the widespread training of economists in educational institutions of various profiles. The effectiveness of the educational process is largely determined by the teaching methodology.

Methodology is a branch of pedagogical science that studies the patterns of teaching a particular academic subjects. The subject of teaching methodology is the very process of teaching a certain academic discipline.

At the moment, the lecture is the leading form of the educational process in higher education, which determines its content. A practical lesson or a seminar is the result of an independent study of the recommended literature, it allows you to exchange opinions in a free environment, to find out what is not yet completely clear and assimilated [6].

The role of independent work in the system of higher education is growing. Independent work of students in economic disciplines is aimed at developing a system of measures for training and education that form economic education and independent thinking of students. High-quality organization of control is the key to stimulating the student to obtain the necessary knowledge.

References:

1. Andreev E.G. Pedagogy in the work of a lecturer. M., 2014.
2. Baranov S.P., Principles of teaching. M., 2015.
3. Brunner D. Learning process. Per. with him. M., 2022.
4. Choice of teaching methods / Ed. Yu. K. Babanski, M., 2021.
5. Zinoviev S. I. Lecture in the higher school. Ed. 3rd. M., 2018.
6. Zotov I.S. Some questions of the method of reading lectures on social sciences at the university. M., 2021.